

Synthesis, Spectral and Potentiometric Studies on 7-(α -Substituted-benzimidazolyl)-8-hydroxyquinolines

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Some new chelating agents containing both quinoline and benzimidazole groups, i.e. α -2-benzimidazolyl- α' -7-(8-hydroxy)quinolinodimethylamine (BMQH, 1), and its nitro (2) and ethyl (3) substituted derivatives have been prepared. Their elemental analysis, electronic, ir and mass spectral studies have been reported. The stepwise acid dissociation constants of the compounds in water-ethanol at 30° and constant ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1$, maintained by using KNO_3) have been determined.

THE 8-hydroxyquinoline¹, benzimidazole² and their derivatives have long been established as potential antibacterial agents and drugs. The role of mixed ligand complexes³ in biological processes have been well recognised. The present paper describes some new compounds containing these coordination groups which are also most stable ones involving organic ligands. Recently, quinolinosulphonamides⁴ have been prepared for their therapeutic values. But no work has yet been reported with ligands containing both the quinoline and benzimidazole groups.

The ligands were prepared by Mannich type reaction⁵ with benzimidazolylalkylamines, formaldehyde and 8-hydroxyquinoline when 7-substituted-8-hydroxyquinolines are obtained.

- 1 ; $R_1 = \text{H}$, $X = \text{CH}_2$
2 ; $R_1 = 5$ (or 6)- NO_2 , $X = \text{CH}_2$
3 ; $R_1 = \text{H}$, $X = \text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$

Experimental

All reagents used were of A.R. grade or properly purified. The solutions for potentiometric titrations were made in double-distilled CO_2 -free water and purified ethanol⁶.

The ligands were prepared by adding formaldehyde to benzimidazolylalkylamines⁷ (0.02 mol each) in ethanol with constant stirring. The mixture was then cooled in ice and 8-hydroxyquinoline (0.02 mol) in ethanol was added. The total volume was kept 50–60 ml and pH adjusted to 5–6. The resulting solid was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol and dried. Melting points were determined in open capillary tube and are uncorrected.

The compounds were found insoluble in water and sparingly soluble in ethanol and acetone. All of them⁸ gave green colouration with FeCl_3 solution and yellow to brown colouration with concentrated H_2SO_4 and concentrated HNO_3 . The elemental analysis, electronic, ir and mass spectra were determined at R.S.I.C., C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Elemental analyses of BMQH (1; yellowish white, m.p. 240°), NBMQH (2; brown, m.p. 184°) and BEQH (3; yellowish white, m.p. 150°) were found

Scheme 1

satisfactory. The main mass spectral fragmentation patterns of BMQH and NBMQH are depicted in Scheme 1 (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - MASS SPECTRAL DATA

(Arranged to display the coincidence of fragment ions in compounds)

Fragmentation process (Scheme 1)	BMQH <i>m/z</i>	NBMQH	
		<i>m'/z</i>	<i>m'-NO₂/z</i>
(a)	75/76/77/78	1 3/124	75/76/77/78
(b), (c)	89/90/91/92	137/138	89/90/91/92
(d)	102/103/104/105	153/154/155	105/106/107/108
(a')	117	163/164	117
(b')	170/171/172/173		
(c')	157/158/159		

Potentiometric titrations of 50 ml portions in (1 : 1) water-ethanol of the following mixtures were carried out with 0.1 M KOH solution at 30° at constant ionic strength ($\mu=0.1$) maintained by using KNO₃: (i) 0.01 M HNO₃, (ii) 0.01 M HNO₃+0.005 M RH₂⁺, (iii) 0.01 M HNO₃+0.002 M RH₂⁺.

pH was measured on a Elico LI-10T pH meter. Duplicate titrations were made in each case under identical conditions. Titration curves pH vs volume of alkali added were plotted. Formation functions $\bar{n}$ (average number of H⁺ bound to ligand R⁻) were calculated by procedure of Irving-Rossotti using pH-titration curves⁸. The stepwise acid dissociation constants pK_1^H , pK_2^H , pK_3^H and pK_4^H values (when $\bar{n}=3.5, 2.5, 1.5$ and 0.5 respectively) were evaluated by graphical methods (Table 2).

and BEQH. The absorption extends to visible region due to nitro substitution¹² at 320 (log ϵ 4.2) and 405 nm (4.39).

The mass spectra of two compounds BMQH and NBMQH were also recorded in order to give further support to the structure and to study their fragmentation patterns. Both of them did not give molecular ions probably because of highly branched molecular structure with a long alkyl chain⁹ (Bz-CH₂-NH-CH₂-QH). The base peaks are obtained at respective *m/z* values obtained by loss of benzimidazole moiety (base peak, *m/z* 171, M-Bz-CH₂) in the case of BMQH and NBMQH, the quinoline ring is cleaved initially (*m/z* 206, M-QH) and ion due to benzimidazole moiety then undergoes a variety of fragmentations (base peak, *m/z* 153) as shown in Scheme 1. The main fragmentation processes¹³ involves rupture of 1,9 and 3,8, 1,9 and 2,3, 1,2 and 3,8 and 1,2 and 2,3 bonds of benzimidazole nucleus. Substituents such as nitro group with or without *ortho*-amino function should, in principle, exhibit their well-known behaviour under electron impact¹⁴. Here the predominant pathway of further breakdown appears to be mediated through nitro group. Data in Table 1 show that one of the other important losses from molecular ions was due to NO₂ radical.

A comparative study of pK_4^H , pK_3^H , pK_2^H and pK_1^H values of the ligands RH₂⁺ with those of benzimidazole, 8-hydroxyquinoline and some of their derivatives reveals that pK_3^H and pK_2^H correspond to the proton of tertiary nitrogen (pyridyl group) of quino-

TABLE 2 - ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF RH₂⁺

Compd.	Temp. °C	μ	Solvent* % (v/v)	pK_4^H	pK_3^H	pK_2^H	pK_1^H
Benzimidazole	25	0.1	60 M-W				5.48 ^a
2-Methyl-benzimidazole	25	0.1	60 M-W				6.19 ^a
2-(2-Pyridyl)benzimidazole							3.44 ^b
8-Hydroxy-quinoline	30	0.05	75 E-W			4.31	11.30 ^c
						3.97	11.48 ^d
							11.07 ^e
BMQH (1)	30	0.01	50 Py-W				11.95
NBMQH (2)		0.1	50 E-W		2.55	5.15	9.50
BEQH (3)				2.40	3.35	5.35	-

* (M) - Methanol, (E) - Ethanol, (Py) - Pyridine.

Ref. 15. ^bRef. 16. ^cRef. 17. ^dRef. 18. ^eRef. 19.

Results and Discussion

The structure of the compounds was elucidated on the basis of elemental analysis, electronic, ir and mass spectral data. The ir spectra showed a broad and strong band around 3500-3400 cm⁻¹ due to NH and OH stretching frequencies. The other characteristic bands due to C=N at 1640-1610 cm⁻¹, benzene ring at 1595-1550 cm⁻¹, anti and symmetric aromatic NO₂ at 1550 and 1335 cm⁻¹ (in NBMQH) and phenolic C-O stretch at 1290-1285 cm⁻¹ were also observed⁹⁻¹¹.

The electronic spectra in ethanol showed principal maxima around 250 nm (log ϵ 4.25) in BMQH

line ring and that of benzimidazole group respectively (Table 2). The pK_1^H value is due to phenolic OH group in quinoline ring. The basicity of the aliphatic imino group is lowered to such an extent ($pK_4^H < 2.0$) that it showed no uptake of proton even from highly acidic medium. A sharp decrease in pK_2^H value in NBMQH is due to electron-withdrawing effect (-I) of nitro substitution in benzimidazole ring. The pK_3^H value is lowered and could not be determined. In BEQH, the interposition of electron-donating ethyl group (+I) between two ring systems increases the pK_3^H values comparatively and pK_4^H value comes out to be 2.4. But pK_1^H value

could not be determined due to precipitation at higher pH during titration

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References

- 1 D. R. H. GOURLEY in "Medicinal Chemistry", ed E. BURFER, Wiley Interscience, New York, 1960; A. ALBERT, "Selective Toxicity", Chapman and Hall, London, 1979
- 2 S. BAHADUR, A K GOEL and R. S. VERMA, *J Indian Chem Soc.*, 1976, 53, 116; A. K. SENGUPTA and H K MISRA, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, 58, 508; J. S. SUKLA, H. H. SINGH and S. S. PARMAR, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1969, 311, 187.
- 3 M. T. BECK, "Chemistry of Complex Equilibria", Van Nostrand-Reinhold, London, 1970.
- 4 K K CHATURVEDI and M GOYAL, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, 61, 175
- 5 J P. PHILLIPS R KEOWN and Q FRENAND, *J Am Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 4306.
- 6 A I VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Chemistry", ELBS, London, 1956, p 166
- 7 L A CESCONE and A R DAY, *J Org Chem.*, 1964, 27, 581
- 8 J BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", Hasse, Copenhagen, 1941; M CALVIN and K. W. WILSON, *J. Am. Chem Soc.*, 1945, 67, 2003; H. M. IRVING and H S ROSSOTTI, *J Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904; 1953, 3397.
- 9 W KEMP, "Organic Spectroscopy", ELBS, Macmillan, 1986.
- 10 L J BELLAMY, "The Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1958
11. L J BELLAMY, "Advances in Infrared Group Frequencies", Chapman and Hall London, 1975.
- 12 J H RIDD and B. V SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 1363.
- 13 H OGURA and S. SUGIMOTO, *Org. Mass Spectrom.*, 1970, 3, 1341, Q N. PORTERAAND and J. BALDAS, "Mass Spectrometry of Heterocyclic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1970, p 532, F. W. MACLAFFERTY, "Interpretation of Mass Spectra", Benjamin", New York, 1966.
- 14 R N SILVERSTEIN, G C. BASSLER and T . MORRILL, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", Wiley, New York, 1974, p 33
15. H. M JAFER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, 53, 191.
16. T. R. HARKINS, J. L WALTER and H. FREISER, *J. Am. Chem Soc.*, 1956, 78, 1143.
17. Y ANJANEYULU, R. Y. SWAMY and R. P. RAO, *J Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 346.
18. H F. STREGER and A. CORSINI, *J Inorg Nucl. Chem.*, 1984, 93, 131
19. P K JADHAV, T. D. MATHEWS and P. V. KAMAT, *J Indian Chem. Soc.* 1986, 63, 894